

A simple exercise in quantifying the number of Diamond BLASTp results within genomes

Clark, C. M. A simple exercise in quantifying the number of Diamond BLASTp results within genomes. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6246156>

Purpose

To demonstrate how many results can be expected when performing bi-directional BLASTp on proteins from a set of *Micromonospora* genomes.

Methods

226 *Micromonospora* genomes were downloaded from RefSeq and all proteins extracted (protein information, including accessions, is available in the accompanying file `301b4dd16967ca06c696323a418d7840.protein_info`). A non-redundant set of proteins was created by removing all but one representative for all completely-identical sequences, resulting in 1,076,690 unique protein sequences. These were then subject to bi-directional BLASTp using `diamond`. `diamond` parameters were default except for `--max-target-seqs` which was set to 0 (“Setting this to... 0 will report all targets for which alignments were found.” source: <https://github.com/bbuchfink/diamond/wiki/3.-Command-line-options>) and the output format which was set to `blast6`.

- Buchfink B, Reuter K, Drost HG, “Sensitive protein alignments at tree-of-life scale using DIAMOND”, *Nature Methods* 18, 366–368 (2021). doi:10.1038/s41592-021-01101-x

This resulted in a 45.3 GB tsv file with 421,865,546 results.

Results

Summary of percent identity values

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
##	17.50	33.90	41.10	50.23	66.00	100.00

Summary of alignment lengths

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
##	15.0	205.0	260.0	318.5	380.0	19147.0

Summary of bitscores

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
##	34.7	97.4	164.0	266.8	320.0	35327.0

Summary of the number of matches per query protein

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
##	1.0	104.0	177.0	391.9	342.0	9303.0

